

Study of applicability of polymer membranes in selective removal of transition metal ions from sea water

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Abstract : This paper investigates the applicability of polymer membranes as molecular sieve, for removal of transition metal ions from sea water, without affecting the sodium ion concentration. The metal ion separation by the polymer membrane takes place on the basis of molecular size of hydrated ion.

Keywords : Polymer membrane, transition metal ion, sea water.

Membrane based separation processes being simple, efficient, clean and compact; have high significance in today's world of science and technology¹. In the field of desalination of sea water, it now assumes pivotal role².

Desalination involves removal of all minerals from sea water. But here, we have investigated the ability of the membrane in selective removal of transition metal ions, without affecting the Na⁺ concentration. The saline water thus produced is free from transition metal ions and can safely be used in production of edible table salt (i.e. salt pan industry) without any fear of contamination. This becomes more relevant due to the fact that sea coasts are one of the most polluted places on this planet.

The idea behind this investigation is to use a non-ionexchange membrane as a molecular sieve in the selective separation of metal ions from sea water without affecting its Na⁺ concentration. The method can also be selectively adapted for any separation process based on molecular/ionic size.

The effectiveness of the membrane in separation of the transition metal ions namely Fe⁺, total iron and Ni²⁺ were observed. Change in Na⁺ and total hardness concentration were also noted.

Theoretical models³ are evolving, suggesting wide variation in membrane transport characteristics of various types of ions; thus supporting this idea of selective separations of ions using polymer membrane.

Experimental

A major percentage of the input sea water is sucked through the membrane. The remaining water is discarded as concentrate. The hydrated transition metal ions being larger in size, preferentially remains in the concentrate. Evidently, the water percolated through the membrane is free from these transition metal ions and is pure saline water (more fit for edible table salt production). Here, we refer this water as 'product'. The basic idea behind the process has been illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Basic operation of a membrane based separation process.

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The whole operation is performed using a Membrane Filtration Unit (MFU) which essentially consists of two glass chambers. The upper one holds the input solution while the lower one receives the output solution. Between these two chambers, the membrane is positioned. The lower chamber is connected to a vacuum pump which creates a constant pressure difference across the membrane, forcing sea water to percolate through the membrane.

However, in a commercial scenario, the opposite action is performed i.e. the sea water is pushed under high pressure through the membrane. But since we are interested only in the effectiveness of the membrane in selective separation of the transition metal ions from sea water (without affecting the Na^+ concentration), so our set up remains relevant albeit certain assumptions.

Since a low pressure is maintained in the lower chamber, some of the product solution inevitably evaporates, increasing the metal ion concentration. So, all calculations were performed in terms of volume of input solution (i.e. sea water) consumed/percolated.

The membrane was used in the process :

Polycarbonate membrane (pore size 0.01 μm), supplied by STERLITECH® CORPORATION. The metal ion concentrations monitored in the input and output solutions from the unit are Fe^{2+} , total iron, Ni^{2+} and Na^+ . Other parameter evaluated was total hardness. Fe^{2+} and total iron concentrations were estimated by 1,10-phenanthroline method (spectrophotometric method)⁵. Ni^{2+} was estimated by alkaline DMG based spectrophotometric method⁴. Total hardness was estimated by EDTA complexometric titration⁵. Na^+ was estimated by Flame Photometry⁶.

Results and discussion

The sea water was collected from Marina Beach (Chennai, India) at the Cooum river end, on February 13, 2006 at 6.30 p.m. The sea water was percolated through the polycarbonate membrane, under 20 Hg (pressure) mm at 27 °C (p/c 0.166) (p/c refers to ratio of volume of product solution to the concentrate solution). The metal ion concentrations and hardness of the 'product' solution was analysed and compared to that of the raw sea water.

The percentage reduction of these metal ions as well as the percentage reduction in total hardness has been listed as below :

	Concentration in untreated sea water (mg/L or ppm)	Concentration in sea water percolated through the membrane under above conditions (mg/L or ppm)	Rejection of the solute achieved by the membrane (%)
Ferrous iron or Fe^{2+}	2.6 ppm	b.d.L	~ 100
Total iron (Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+})	3.8 ppm	2.766 ppm	27.2
Total hardness	9088 ppm of CaCO_3	7810 ppm of CaCO_3	14.06
Ni^{2+}	6.1538 ppm	~ 0.00 ppm	100
Na^+	10.5 ppt ^a	10.48 ppt	0.19

^appt – parts per thousands.

The hydrated transition metal ions, due to their much bigger size than the hydrated Na^+ , gets separated more effectively by the membrane. Thus, the water percolated through the membrane (product solution) remains poor in transition metal ion concentration, while the remaining un-percolated water (concentrate) retains these transition metal ions. The Na^+ concentration in the 'product' practically remains unchanged.

Conclusion :

The presented work shows the ability of the membrane to selectively separate ions from solutions, based on their hydrated ion size. Here, it is evident that the hydrated sodium ions being smaller than the hydrated transition metal ions, easily pass through the membrane; while the hydrated transition metal ions being larger in size, fails to permeate through the membrane and thus gets discarded with the concentrate.

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Note

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